

Exploiting Peer Trust and Semantic Similarities in the Assignment Assessment Process

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Abstract. In many scenarios, the assessment by a single expert of all the content produced by an individual may be impractical due to the overall vast amount of content to be assessed by the expert. Examples are, for instance, online education services with thousands of students or scientific papers submitted to a conference that have to be assessed by program chairs in a short time period. Leveraging peer evaluations is a crucial strategy to mitigate assessment burdens and reduce the time required to deliver the expected results. This paper revisits the foundational concept of Personalised Automated Assessment (PAAS), which seeks to approximate the assessments of a particular community member, known as the leader, by integrating the peer assessments among the other community members of their answers to an assignment. Our extension of PAAS enhances its machine learning capabilities by integrating in the algorithm the semantic similarity among peer assessments to improve its prediction power. Experimental validation using synthetic and real-world datasets shows the efficacy of our extension, reducing prediction errors and increasing accuracy, especially in scenarios where the several assignments are significantly similar with one another.

Keywords: Community assessment · trust and reputation · collective intelligence

1 Introduction

In many real-life situations, we find people who must deal with the problem of evaluating many objects or items. In practice, such a task often becomes unbearable for an individual due to the sheer volume of information that needs to be assessed. The realm of education and academia provides us with many examples. Consider, for instance, a teacher offering an online course that hundreds of students attend. In this scenario, the teacher might need to evaluate assignments³ twice or thrice as many as the number of students. Naturally, expecting a single person to assess all assignments within a short time frame is untenable. Another

³ In this paper, we will use the term *assignment* to refer to the actual *answer* that a particular student provides for an assignment.

representative example is journal paper reviews, where the editor must evaluate many papers. In such contexts, exploiting peer evaluations can substantially mitigate the evaluation burden and assist evaluators in meeting deadlines.

This paper revisits the Personalised Automated Assessment (PAAS) concept, introduced in [7]. Gutierrez et al., in the context of education, proposed a model for alleviating the evaluation burden of one person (called the leader of a community) by using peer assessments (i.e., assessments made by other members of the community). In particular, PAAS incorporates information from assignments assessed by both the leader and the peers. Essentially, PAAS models the leader’s trust in the peers’ assessments and learns how much the leader should trust each of their peers based on their commonly assessed assignments. Then, it predicts the leader’s assessment of an assignment based on the assessments of that very same assignment made by others. In the context of a multiagent system, PAAS can also be used to model the trust that humans have in software agents that assess assignments.

This work extends PAAS to enhance the model’s learning and prediction capabilities using the evaluations made and information about the assignments. As noted by the authors in [7], using semantic similarities of assignments is a promising extension. Thus, inspired by [7], we extend PAAS in this direction and put forward the *Extended Peer Automated Assessment* (EPAAS) model. Specifically, EPAAS incorporates semantic similarities among assessed assignments to enhance predictive accuracy. Unlike the previous approach, which is limited to commonly evaluated assignments, our proposal learns from similar assignments, adapting its openness to learn based on the strength of trust in a peer.

To confirm the effectiveness of our proposed model, we conducted an empirical evaluation considering both synthetic and real-world data. The results show that our extended model, EPAAS, is more accurate than PAAS, i.e., it exhibits lower prediction error. Additionally, our empirical evaluation showed that the improvement in prediction is more significant for fewer evaluated assignments. Therefore, EPAAS can give us a great advantage when dealing with a low number of assessments.

The paper is organised as follows. In Section 2, we briefly review related work. Section 3 describes the foundational ideas behind the PAAS algorithm, Section 4 presents the extension proposed to the original model, and Section 5 summarises the experimental results that validate the improvements of the extended model. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper.

2 Related Work

There exists extensive research on the concept of trust and how to model it; especially within the context of teamwork. [6] describes trust as “the shared willingness of the team members” to be exposed to other members’ actions (and accept the corresponding consequences) with the understanding the other members act on behalf of the team without being subject to be monitored or controlled, as defined in [10] and [5]. Also, the team member’s expectation that others will carry

out actions that relevant to the team, and is represented by the predictability of the members doing a task.

From a computational point of view, several researches focused on trust representation to model the predictability, and use it for making predictions. In the context of assessments generation based on peer evaluations, literature provides plenty of research following this approach. Alfaro and Shavlovsky in [2] introduced CrowdGrader, a crowdsourcing algorithm that aggregates assessments from multiple students into an overall assessment for an assignment, utilising a reputation system to measure students' accuracy degrees. PeerRank [18] computes the grade of an agent as a weighted average of the grades it receives from other agents, similar to the PageRank method for web pages. Using probabilistic models, Piech et al. [13] propose a method to estimate student reliability and correct biases in online learning scenarios. Wu et al. [19] investigate consensus building among experts in a trust network and provide visual consensus models.

Following a statistical approach for score prediction, Bachrach et al. [4] employ a Bayesian model to grade tests, estimating the probability of a participant knowing the correct answer. It models the probability of participant answers based on the correct answer and their knowledge. Sterbini and Temperini [16] utilise peer evaluation among students to aid teachers in grading open answers, representing each student as a triplet of discrete variables: knowledge, judgment, and correctness. Ashley and Goldin [3] devise a hierarchical Bayesian model for mining peer assessment data, accounting for graders' biases and using the resulting posterior distribution to answer queries regarding rubric criteria suitability.

The PAAS model [7] differs by computing automated assessments from the perspective of a specific community member, aiming to estimate assessments accurately rather than achieve consensus. PAAS aggregates peer assessments, giving trusted peers more weight, and uses probability distributions to build trust metrics. The proposed model was compared with the collaborative filtering algorithms [9] for the same task, outperforming it by increasing the number of assessments and achieving a lower prediction error.

In [1], Lopez et al. propose a reconciliation between Bayesian inference and the PAAS trust model. The proposed PG -bivariate evaluation model considers the correlations between any pair of peers who have some commonly evaluated assessment, based on the PG_1 -bias model [13].

This work propose an extension of the PAAS model proposed in [7], hence the following section below discusses the necessary background regarding the PAAS model.

3 The PAAS Model

The Personalised Automated Assessments (PAAS) model [7] is a trust-based model that aims to predict future evaluations on assignments as accurately as possible. Given an agent of interest, referred to as *leader* and denoted as ϵ , PAAS predicts how ϵ will evaluate some assignment α . The prediction is based on ϵ 's peers evaluations over α . In some detail, PAAS exploits past evaluations over

assignments, compares leader’s evaluations against peers’ evaluations and builds a trust model that estimates how much the leader should trust the assessments made by their peers. Hence, PAAS predicts the leader’s evaluation of a new, unseen assignment based on the trust model.

Let \mathcal{P} be the set of peers and \mathcal{I} be the set of assignments. With $e_\mu^\alpha \in \mathcal{E}$ we denote the evaluation (also referred to as assessment, interchangeably) made by agent $\mu \in \{\epsilon\} \cup \mathcal{P}$ over the assignment $\alpha \in I$, where \mathcal{E} is a discrete and ordered evaluation space. An automated assessment for the leader ϵ over assignment $\alpha \in \mathcal{I}$ is represented by a probability distribution $\mathbb{P} = \{x_1 \mapsto v_1, x_2 \mapsto v_2, \dots, x_n \mapsto v_n\}$, where $x_i \in \mathcal{E}$, $n = |\mathcal{E}|$, and $v_i \in [0, 1]$ such that $\sum_{i=1}^n v_i = 1$. Here, v_i denotes the probability of ϵ ’s evaluation over α being x_i .

Given a set of peer assessments over α , denoted as \mathcal{O}^α , PAAS estimates ϵ ’s evaluation of α by aggregating the particular evaluations $p(X^\alpha = x | \mathcal{O}^\alpha)$ (see below in Section 3.2).

3.1 Trust

The trust between peers can be built if the peers have evaluated at least one common assignment. That is, given two agents $i, j \in \{\epsilon\} \cup \mathcal{P}$, PAAS can build a trust model between i and j if there is an assignment $\alpha \in \mathcal{I}$ such that i has evaluated α with e_i^α and j with e_j^α . The evaluation difference between evaluations is estimated using the Euclidean distance:

$$\text{diff}(e_i^\alpha, e_j^\alpha) = e_i^\alpha - e_j^\alpha \quad (1)$$

If $\text{diff}(e_i^\alpha, e_j^\alpha) = 0$, it means that i and j give the *same* evaluation.⁴ If $\text{diff}(e_i^\alpha, e_j^\alpha) < 0$ it means that i *underrates* α with respect to j and if $\text{diff}(e_i^\alpha, e_j^\alpha) > 0$ it means that i *overrates* α with respect to j . To express the trust between i and j , PAAS builds a probability distribution (denoted as $\mathbb{T}_{i,j}$) over all possible evaluation differences. Formally, given the ordered evaluation space $\mathcal{E} = [0, m]$, trust is a probability distribution over possible evaluations’ differences, that is, over the interval $[-m, m]$. The ignorance distribution (\mathbb{F}) is the default trust distribution between two peers over the space of differences is the one that results from the sampling of values over two flat distributions (i.e., a distribution where giving any mark is equally probable) within the evaluation interval \mathcal{E} . A trust model \mathbb{T} is a set of trust distributions among all evaluators $\{\epsilon\} \cup \mathcal{P}$, i.e.,

$$\mathbb{T} = \{\mathbb{T}_{i,j} \text{ for every pair } i, j \in \{\epsilon\} \cup \mathcal{P}\}.$$

Direct trust When two agents $i, j \in \{\epsilon\} \cup \mathcal{P}$ evaluate the same assignment $\alpha \in \mathcal{I}$, then the *direct* trust of i towards j , $\mathbb{T}_{i,j}$, can be updated.⁵ Let x be the evaluation distance between agents i and j over an assessment α , $x = \text{diff}(e_i^\alpha, e_j^\alpha)$. Then the probability of x in $\mathbb{T}_{i,j}$ is updated as follows:

$$p(X_j = x) := p(X_j = x) + \gamma * (1 - p(X_j = x)) \quad (2)$$

⁴ This is the only scenario where $\text{diff}(e_i^\alpha, e_j^\alpha) = \text{diff}(e_j^\alpha, e_i^\alpha)$.

⁵ Similarly, we can update the direct trust $\mathbb{T}_{j,i}$.

In Eq 2, $\gamma \in [0, 1]$ limits the potential growth of the probability $p(X_j = x)$. This value determines how fast the trust of i over j will grow. After updating $p(X_j = x)$, the trust distribution $\mathbb{T}_{i,j}$ is normalised using an entropy-based approach [15]. This entropy-based normalisation approach intends to preserve the existing trust distribution's shape by proportionally decreasing the value $p(X^\alpha = y)$ for $y \neq x$. However, this could introduce a bias towards a previously high probability of evaluation difference. Nonetheless, even though addressing this bias problem is worth further study, it is not within the scope of this paper.

Indirect trust On the other hand, when two agents $i, j \in \{\epsilon\} \cup \mathcal{P}$ share no common evaluated assignments, then the trust of i towards j , $\mathbb{T}_{i,j}$, needs to be *indirectly* updated. The model adopts the idea of transitive trust based on the Eigentrust algorithm introduced in [8]. PAAS defines the operators to compute the transitive trust distribution from two distributions in an additive manner, finding $\mathbb{T}_{i,k}$ given $\mathbb{T}_{i,j}$ and $\mathbb{T}_{j,k}$. From a probabilistic perspective, if x represents the difference in evaluations between i and j , and y represents the difference in assessment between j and k , the difference in evaluations between i and k can be described as an aggregation of the probabilities $P(x)$ and $P(y)$.

Given the trust distributions \mathbb{P} and \mathbb{Q} over the numeric interval $[-m, m]$ (i.e., the evaluation difference between two evaluations falls in $[-m, m]$), the combined distance distribution, $\mathbb{R} = \mathbb{P} \otimes \mathbb{Q}$, is defined as follows:

$$r(X = z) = \begin{cases} \sum_{x+y=z} p(X = x) * q(X = y) & \text{if } z \in (-m, m) \\ \sum_{x+y \leq -m} p(X = x) * q(X = y) & \text{if } z = -m \\ \sum_{x+y \geq m} p(X = x) * q(X = y) & \text{if } z = m \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

and then apply Eq 2 to later normalise to compute the new trust distribution.

Finally, when more than one peer shares common evaluations with the leader and the indirect peer, PAAS selects the peer whose trust distribution is closest to the ideal trust distribution: $p(X = 0) = 1$. The earth mover's distance (*EMD*) presented in [14] is used to compute the distance between a trust distribution and the ideal one.

3.2 Decision

The primary purpose of PAAS is to evaluate assignments that the leader has not previously assessed. In other words, given a peer μ 's evaluation of an assignment e_μ^α , PAAS determines the probability that ϵ evaluates α as x , denoted as $p(X^\alpha =$

$x|e_\mu^\alpha$). The method for calculating this conditional probability is:

$$p(X = x|e_\mu^\alpha) = \begin{cases} \sum_{y \leq \text{diff}(x, e_\mu^\alpha)} \mathbb{T}_{\epsilon, \mu}(y) & \text{if } x = 0 \\ \sum_{y \geq \text{diff}(x, e_\mu^\alpha)} \mathbb{T}_{\epsilon, \mu}(y) & \text{if } x = m \\ \mathbb{T}_{\epsilon, \mu}(\text{diff}(x, e_\mu^\alpha)) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

When many peers give an evaluation about the same assignment $\mathcal{O}^\alpha = \{e_{\mu_1}^\alpha, e_{\mu_2}^\alpha, \dots, e_{\mu_n}^\alpha\}$, if the trust level is high enough, then those evaluations are used to estimate ϵ 's evaluation. Let $\mathcal{Y}(\mathbb{T}_{i,j})$ denote the earth movers' distance between a given distribution and the ignorance distribution, i.e., $\mathcal{Y}(\mathbb{T}_{i,j}) = \text{EMD}(\mathbb{T}_{i,j}, \mathbb{F})$. The evaluations \mathcal{O}^α will contribute in predicting the leader's evaluation over α , if and only if the distance of the trust distributions \mathbb{T}_{e, μ_i} exceeds a minimum acceptable value of trust $\delta \in (0, 0.1)$:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \mathcal{Y}(\mathbb{T}_{\epsilon, \mu_i}) > \delta \quad (5)$$

If the restriction is fulfilled, the value of $p(X^\alpha = x|\mathcal{O}^\alpha)$ is defined by using:

$$p(X = x|\mathcal{O}^\alpha) = \left\{ \bigvee_{i=1}^n (\mathcal{Y}(\mathbb{T}_{\epsilon, \mu_i}) * p(X = x|e_{\mu_i}^\alpha)) \right. \quad (6)$$

If set \mathcal{O}^α does not fulfil the minimum trust value δ , then $p(X^\alpha = x)$ will be the ignorance distribution, $p(X = x|\mathcal{O}^\alpha) = 1/n$. The operator \vee combines the probabilities, assuming the sources are independent: $a \vee b = a + b - a \cdot b$. This assumption is made considering the case when evaluators do not know each other.

From the model description, the trust between two evaluators is built only based on the commonly evaluated assessments, ignoring similarities between the assessment content. This behaviour also excludes information from "isolated" peers from the model, i.e., peers who share no common assignments to assess.

4 The Extended PAAS Model

As mentioned earlier, the PAAS model excludes assignments that both peers have not evaluated when updating the trust between two peers. If a peer $q \in \mathcal{P}$ has assessed a set of assignments $s \subset \mathcal{I}$, and the intersection between s and the set of assignments assessed by any other peer (including the leader) is empty, then all assessments made by q are disregarded. Moreover, the current model of PAAS entirely ignores any information that can be extracted from comparing evaluations over non-identical assignments. We believe that such information can significantly contribute to the trust model. To overcome the limitations above,

we present the *Extended Personalised Automated Assessment (EPAAS)* model in this section.

Incorporating similarities between assignments into the PAAS model addresses the issues above. It opens up a path for estimating the evaluation of assignments that none of the peers have assessed previously. Under the assumption that similar assignments are similarly evaluated, we propose a method to estimate the most likely evaluations considering all evaluators $\{\epsilon \cup \mathcal{P}\}$.

We assume the existence of a similarity function $f(\alpha, \sigma) \in [0, 1]$ for comparing any pair of assignments $\alpha, \sigma \in \mathcal{I}$. Defining a proper similarity function can also be a very complex task that requires the knowledge of experts in the field. However, AI provides several tools to ease the task under certain conditions. Let us assume that an assignment is given in a textual form or that a finite set of features can describe it. In such cases, we can exploit existing tools to define a similarity function rather easily. For example, we can use text analysis software to measure the similarity between texts (such as FastText [11]) or vector distance metrics such as the Jaccardian [12] or the cosine distance, words etc. to measure similarity between feature vectors. Thus, defining a proper similarity function may not be hard under certain conditions. Nonetheless, we highlight that regardless of the assignments' space, the only required properties for the similarity function are *(i)* positivity, *(ii)* symmetry and *(iii)* maximality when two assignments are identical.

Thus, similarity-based trust allows for building trust with indirect peers,⁶ bypassing the commonly direct peers. This is a desired functionality, especially if an indirect peer shares no common evaluations with the leader or any other peer. Furthermore, it allows us to extract useful information from evaluations of assignments that are not identical but similar enough. We assume that every evaluator uses the same similarity function.⁷

Notably, even though with EPAAS, we can build trust models for indirect peers without considering the direct ones, we do not disregard the indirect trust functionality of PAAS. Instead, we combine the similarity-based and indirect trust (if we can compute it) and keep the strongest one by using Eq 5 and 6.

4.1 Similar assignments

To update the trust of one peer towards another when we consider semantic similarities, we modify Eq 2. Specifically, we alter the potential growth of the trust distribution between i and j so that it is flexible to learn from similar assignments. The potential growth is denoted with κ and is given by:

$$\kappa(p, x) = \gamma * (1 - p(X_j = x)) * \eta \quad (7)$$

Then Eq 2 becomes:

$$p(X_j = x) := p(X_j = x) + \kappa(p, x) \quad (8)$$

⁶ We say *direct peers* to refer to those peers with whom a peer can compute a direct trust, and say *indirect peers* to those with whom a peer can build an indirect trust.

⁷ We could extend the approach by using a custom similarity function for each peer.

In Eq 7, $\eta \in [0, 1]$ represents the contribution based on the similarity between evaluated assignments and regulates the contribution similarly to γ . The value of η varies depending on the similarity between the evaluated assignments (α by i and σ by j) at hand. However, it is natural to assume that increasing the contribution linearly based on the similarity of elements does not accurately reflect how trust evolves. Intuitively, the weaker the trust, the less likely a human will adopt others' opinions. Following this idea, it is proposed to learn based on the similarity between the assignments and how strong the current trust is.

$$\eta = f(\alpha, \sigma)^{-1/\log_b(z(p))} \quad (9)$$

Eq 9 follows the idea that if two assignments are similar, they should have similar evaluations. Based on the intuition that a peer is more open to learning from similar assignments as the trust is stronger, we allow the similarity value to have a greater influence on the potential growth $((1 - p(X = x)))$. The term $z(p)$, referred to as flexibility degree, determines how flexible the trust distribution p is to change based on similar assignments and is defined as:

$$z(p) = \frac{1}{b} + \frac{H(p)}{2 * \log_2(m * 2 + 1)} \quad (10)$$

In Eq 10, the value of b is the base of the logarithm of Eq 9 and $b > 2$ to avoid $z = 1$, then $z \in [1/b, 1)$ ⁸. In other words, b regulates the minimum values of similarity that will contribute to η . The strength of the trust between peers is the entropy $H(p)$ of the distribution p . When $H(p) = 0$, it means that the peers have complete trust, i.e., when the $p(X = x) = 1$ for some specific $x \in [-m, m]$, and therefore, the similarity contributes linearly. Eq 1 presents the contribution

Fig. 1: Trust flexibility degree according to z value

(y axis) of a given similarity value (x axis) according to possible values of z (using

⁸ We recommend using the natural logarithm in Eq 9 and therefore $b \equiv e$.

the natural logarithm: $b = e$). If a peer has a weak trust concerning others, it will be less likely to learn from assignments that are not very similar since the value of $z(p)$ will be lower. The opposite occurs when a strong trust is already built.

It is essential to notice that η 's contribution to the potential growth highly depends on the similarity function. A well-defined similarity function provides more accurate contributions, while a lousy similarity function provides poor contributions. Also, the proposed flexibility degree $z(p)$ is sensitive to the order of presented evaluations. Building trust by starting with the most similar assessments is recommended to get the greatest possible benefit from semantic similarities.

4.2 Final trust for indirect peers

Regarding the trust of the leader towards a direct peer (i.e., peers with commonly evaluated objects), it is clear that EPAAS updates the trust distribution according to Eq 8, i.e., considering the semantic similarities among the objects. In the case of some indirect peer, unlike PAAS, which uses the notion of *indirect trust*, EPAAS can build the trust distribution using again Eq 8. However, in our approach, we do not disregard the indirect trust entirely. Instead, we update the trust distribution towards an indirect peer by selecting the one (indirect vs similarity-based trust) farthest from the ignorance distribution.

Let $i, j \in \{\epsilon\} \cup \mathcal{P}$ be two indirect peers that share no common evaluations. Moreover, let us denote with $\mathbb{T}_{i,j}^{in}$ the indirect trust of i towards j , computed as described in Section 3.1. Similarly, we denote with $\mathbb{T}_{i,j}^{si}$ the corresponding similarity-based trust, computed via Eq 8. Then, for computing the trust $\mathbb{T}_{i,j}$, EPAAS selects the trust distribution between $\mathbb{T}_{i,j}^{si}$ and $\mathbb{T}_{i,j}^{in}$ that differs the most from the ignorance distribution \mathbb{F} . Formally:

$$\mathbb{T}_{i,j} = \max(\mathcal{Y}(\mathbb{T}_{i,j}^{si}), \mathcal{Y}(\mathbb{T}_{i,j}^{in})) \quad (11)$$

where $\mathcal{Y}(\cdot) = EMD(\cdot, \mathbb{F})$ is the earth movers' distance between the trust and the ignorance distribution \mathbb{F} . This way, we exploit both the indirect and the similarity-based trust, while we keep the one that it is less ignorant. Later Eq 6 is used for defining the final trust when many peers give their point of view ($\mathbb{T}_{i,j}$).

5 Empirical Evaluations

This section discusses our empirical evaluation of the proposed model, EPAAS. We conducted several experiments using synthetic and real-world datasets to show the advantages of EPAAS over PAAS. According to Gutierrez et al., [7], the PAAS model's primary goal is to provide the best prediction from the leader's point of view with the minimum amount of assessments from the leader and the peers. Our empirical evaluation yielded EPAAS with lower prediction errors, and

therefore, the results confirm that exploiting semantic similarities can improve the trust model. Next, in Section 5.1, we present the methodology followed during our empirical evaluation, while in Section 5.2, we discuss our results.

5.1 Methodology

Both models (PAAS and EPAAS) were fed with the same input data for comparison purposes. The evaluations of the peers were presented in the initial stage to build a trust distribution for each (ordered) pair $i, j \in \mathcal{P}$. Later, we build the leader’s trust ϵ towards their peers using the two models. Having the set of assignments evaluated by the leader, only the first En initial evaluations are presented to the model. The assessment value $En + 1$ is predicted and compared to the actual value. Afterwards, the model at hand updates the trust distribution with the actual assessment of $En + 1$ before predicting the assessment $En + 2$. This process continues iteratively until a limit for the leader evaluations is reached. The limit for the synthetic dataset is 23 assessments, and the real-world dataset is 12 assessments.

Since the EPAAS model is affected by the order of the assignments presented to assess, we tested both models by giving different assignment orders. We shuffled the leader’s evaluations, generating 1000 different assignment orders. Each order was presented to both models to measure the error in each evaluation step $En + i$. The final result is the mean of the error for each evaluation step $En + i$ in the different provided orders.

5.2 Results

To compute the prediction error for each model result, we use the earth movers’ distance between the model’s at-hand output and the distribution of absolute certainty on the real value.

Synthetic Dataset

For this series of experiments, we generated synthetic datasets. The synthetic datasets were generated following the idea that a set of reviewers needs to assess several journal papers. In this scenario, the journal editor corresponds to the leader ϵ ; the reviewers correspond to the peers \mathcal{P} , while the papers correspond to the assignments \mathcal{I} . In more detail, we synthetically generated data as follows. We assume that from each paper, we can extract a feature vector regarding their English quality, the relevance between keywords and cited literature, the recency of the related work presented, and detected plagiarism. Each feature receives a value in the range $[0, 1]$, with 0 indicating that the paper is very poor in the corresponding feature and 1 indicating that the paper is excellent. Then, the similarity between two papers $a, b \in \mathcal{I}$ is defined as the cosine distance between their feature vectors v_a and v_b :

$$sim(a, b) = \frac{v_a \cdot v_b}{\|v_a\| \cdot \|v_b\|}$$

We generated 900 papers, and for each paper, we generated a random feature vector. To generate the evaluators (i.e., the leader and the reviewers), we were inspired by how people rate movies in IMDB. Specifically, we studied the behaviour of the users described in [17] and designed an evaluators’ profile generator, which we describe below. The leader (journal editor) evaluates 60 papers, while each reviewer evaluates 150 papers, with 30 of them being common with the leader. Let us denote with $X_i \subseteq \mathcal{I}$ the set of papers evaluated by the evaluator $i \in \{\epsilon\} \cup \mathcal{P}$. For each evaluated paper $a \in X_i$, we generate the grade that i gives to a , so that similar papers are graded similarly. Particularly, for each paper $a \in X_i$:

Step 1: we find the most similar paper a^* that has been already marked by i : $a^* = \arg \max_{a' \in X_i^{\text{Graded}}} \text{sim}(a, a')$, where $X_i^{\text{Graded}} \subseteq X_i$ contains the papers already graded by i ; we skip Step 1 if a is the first paper to grade;

Step 2: we randomly draw a number c from the discrete space $[\chi, \psi]$ where

- $\chi = \max \left\{ \text{Grade}_\varepsilon(a^*) - \left((1 - \text{sim}(a, a^*)) \cdot 10, 1 \right) \right\}$,
- $\psi = \min \left\{ \text{Grade}_\varepsilon(a^*) + \left((1 - \text{sim}(a, a^*)) \cdot 10, 10 \right) \right\}$, and
- $\text{Grade}_i(a^*)$ is the grade of paper a^* given already by evaluator i ;

for the first paper $[\chi, \psi] = [1, 10]$.

By generating the leader and the reviewers as described above: (1) we ensure that each evaluator is consistent with themselves regarding the criteria of grading papers, and (2) some reviewers grade papers similarly to the leader, while others grade very differently.

In summary, the synthetic dataset involves:

- 60 evaluations by the leader;
- 14 reviewers;
- 150 evaluations made by each reviewer, 30 of which were common to the leader (i.e., $|X_\varepsilon \cap X_i| = 30$);
- each paper evaluated by some evaluator was graded with a mark from the discrete space $[1, 10]$.

In our simulation, we let the leader ε initially evaluate 2 papers (i.e., $En = 2$). Then, we follow the methodology described in Section 5.1 for 20 more papers. A total number of 22 papers was chosen to observe the behaviour of the models (PAAS and EPAAS) with a small number of assessments. For the leader, we selected 22 papers that have been commonly assessed by the reviewers. In that way, we can guarantee that for every assignment assessed by the leader, at least one peer assessed that paper. In both models, we set the learning rate $\gamma = 0.2$ in order to receive a small impact from the newly presented examples over the current trust distribution.

Figures 2a-2c illustrate the results with 4, 9 and 14 reviewers, respectively. In all cases, the EPAAS has a lower prediction error than PAAS. The error difference increases as the number of evaluated assessments increases because the benefit of the similarities between assessments is bigger. Such a result is expected since more evaluations exist for EPAAS to exploit semantic similarities.

(a) Test results with four peers

(a) Test results with four peers

(b) Test results with nine peers

(b) Test results with nine peers

(c) Test results with fourteen peers

(c) Test results with fourteen peers

Fig. 2: Synthetic Dataset

Fig. 3: Real world dataset

During our simulation, the trust between the reviewers and the editor changes according to the new evaluations provided by the editor. Generally speaking, the trust distribution can be categorised into two main groups: highly trusted peers and poorly trusted peers. The highly trusted peers have a clear evolution towards a certain evaluation difference in the trust space. Conversely, peers with a variable evaluation difference (related to some bias or other criteria not explicitly defined) affect the evolution of trust and are poorly trusted by the leader.

To give a clearer representation of changes in the trust, in Figure 4, we show the evolution of two trust distributions for the steps 5, 10 and 20, including the initial state (ignorance). Note that the x-axis shows the evaluations’ differences space (that range in interval $[-m, m]$, see Section 3), while the y-axis shows the leader’s trust level. Specifically, we pick a reviewer that the editor should trust, based on the grades the reviewer gave on the commonly evaluated with the editor papers. That is, given the grades of the leader for the papers the editor evaluated, we picked the reviewer who had the most similar grading in the commonly evaluated ones. Similarly, we pick a reviewer the leader should not trust since their grading on the commonly evaluated papers is the least similar.

Figure 4a illustrates the trust evolution of the reviewer that the leader should trust (i.e., the one with the most similar grades). On the other hand, Figure 4b illustrates the trust evolution of the reviewer that the editor is not expected to trust. As we can see, the *trusted* reviewer keeps a consistent trust shape and becomes stronger as more evaluations are presented to the model. In contrast, for the *un-trusted* reviewer, starting from the ignorance trust distribution, we observe that as more evaluations are presented to the model, the model becomes more uncertain (exhibits more spikes of similar probabilities). It is worth noticing that for the trusted reviewer, the final trust distribution exhibits one spike that exceeds 0.5, i.e., the leader trusts the reviewer’s grades with high probability. On the other hand, for the un-trusted reviewer, where we have more spikes, they are of lower probabilities (below 0.25). Finally, compared to the PAAS model, Figure 5 depicts the differences between the final trust distribution computed by PAAS (blue line) and EPAAS (orange line) while preserving the ignorance distribution for reference (green line). In this case, we selected from the trusted (a reviewer whose grading differs from the editors’s grading below some threshold) and un-trustee (a reviewer whose grading differs from the leader’s grading above some threshold) reviewers with the highest trust difference between PAAS and EPAAS models. In Figure 5a, we see that for a trusted reviewer, the models computed very similar trust distribution, while Figure 5b for an un-trusted reviewer EPAAS computes a smoother trust distribution than PAAS. Notably, our main observation is that the trust distributions computed by EPAAS have lower entropy than the corresponding ones computed by PAAS. That is, PAAS distributions exhibit more spikes than EPAAS distributions. This behaviour is clearer in the trust distribution for an un-trusted reviewer (see Figure 5b). Thus, EPAAS, using semantic similarities among the different papers, computes trust distributions with higher predictability than PAAS.

Real-world Dataset We used the same dataset as in [7] for this experiment. In this dataset, the authors in [7] gathered information from 30 underage students in two English language classes. The data was gathered from two English language classrooms comprising 30 fourteen-year-old students. The classroom participants were assigned two tasks: (1) an English composition task and (2) a song vocabulary task. For evaluating an assignment, the evaluator at hand needs to assess the assignment according to various criteria specific to each task.

(a) High trust evolution

(b) Low trust evolution

Fig. 4: Trust evolution

That is, for an assignment in the composition task, the evaluators considered the criteria *focus*, *coherence*, and *grammar*; while for an assignment in the song vocabulary task, the evaluators considered the criteria *in-time submission*, *compliance with requirements*, and *lyrical accuracy*. For a given assignment, each criterion could be graded with a number ranging from 1 (very poor) to 4 (excellent); while we assume that the assignment as a whole is marked with the summation of the marks received for each criterion. For example, suppose an assignment in the composition task received marks 3, 4, and 3 for the crite-

(a) High trust difference

(b) Low trust difference

Fig. 5: Trust difference between PAAS and EPAAS

ria focus, coherence, and grammar, respectively. In that case, the assignment is marked with the grade 10 (out of 12). This results in a discrete space for the trust $[-12, 12]$. Each assignment was evaluated by (i) the teacher and (ii) one or more students (different to the student submitting the assignment). In summary, the dataset consists of the following:

- 71 assignments (35 for the English composition task and 36 for the song vocabulary task);
- 71 evaluations made by the teacher (one evaluation per assignment);

- 168 evaluation made by students (each student evaluated on average 2.4 assignments)
- each criterion was graded (per evaluator) with a mark from 1 (very poor) to 4 (excellent); and
- each assignment was graded (per evaluator) with the sum of the marks given to its criteria.

Under the assumption that similar items are evaluated similarly, we build a similarity function for the assignments. In more detail, we consider the teacher’s evaluations (e_t) as the “ground truth”, and, therefore, for two assignments a, b we define the similarity between a and b as:

- if $a = b$ then $sim(a, b) = 1$;
- if $a \neq b$, $Task(a) = Task(b)$ and
 - $e_t^a = e_t^b$ then we draw a random number s from $\mathcal{U}(0.85, 0.95)$ and we set $sim(a, b) = s$;
 - $0 < |e_t^a - e_t^b| \leq 3$ then we draw a random number s from $\mathcal{U}(0.65, 0.84)$ and we set $sim(a, b) = s$;
 - $3 < |e_t^a - e_t^b| \leq 7$ then we draw a random number s from $\mathcal{U}(0.3, 0.5)$ and we set $sim(a, b) = s$;
- otherwise $sim(a, b) = 0$.

After initially defining the similarity degree between all pairs of assignments a, b , the similarity value is not changed during the experiment execution. For this set of experiments, $\gamma = 0.2$ for both models, the teacher (leader) starts with 3 initial evaluated objects ($En = 3$) and 8 additional evaluations were tested. Also, we compare the algorithms with 4, 9 and 14 peers. The results for each case are presented in Figures 3a-3c.

Similarly to the synthetic experiments, the results show that EPAAS has a lower prediction error than PAAS for fewer evaluations, and the error difference increases based on the number of evaluated assessments. Moreover, we observe that as the number of peers increases, the predictions are more accurate (i.e., the error difference is bigger). Such a result is expected since more evaluations exist for EPAAS to exploit semantic similarities. Also, as the number of assessments increases, the results of both algorithms tend to converge because the benefit from similar assessments decreases. Following the principles behind the proposal and the experiment results, we can say that PAAS is the upper bound for EPAAS.

6 Concluding remarks

This work addresses the challenge of comprehensive assessment in expert evaluation scenarios, emphasising the utility of peer evaluations to ease the assessment burdens of a leader. It extends the Personalised Automated Assessment (PAAS) model, enhancing its prediction capabilities by taking advantage of semantic similarities among assignments and peer evaluations. Experimental validation

demonstrates that the Extended PAAS (EPAAS) model outperforms PAAS, particularly in scenarios with similar evaluated assignments. The results highlight the efficacy of EPAAS in reducing prediction errors. When the leader has fewer evaluations, the advantage of EPAAS over PAAS is more significant. Also, when the number of peers' evaluations increases, so does the error gap. However, as the number of evaluated assessments increases, both model errors tend to converge. Therefore, we can consider PAAS to be an upper bound of EPASS.

The proposed approach represents an advancement in automated assessment systems, offering potential applications in various evaluation domains. In future work, we intend to explore the efficiency of EPAAS in accurately predicting yet-to-be-evaluated assignments. Moreover, we would like to improve the trust updating rules and seek better approaches other than the entropy-based normalisation that is currently used. Finally, our model can be applied in other domains beyond education. As such, we aim to use EPAAS as a recommender system in domains such as movie recommendations, media peer-based credibility, etc., and compare it against state-of-the-art recommendation algorithms.

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